

Risk Factors for Meconium Stained Liquor and Outcome of Neonate in Meconium Stained Amniotic Fluid

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Abstract:

Background: Meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSAF) is a significant concern in obstetrics due to its association with adverse neonatal outcomes. Understanding the factors of risk and neonatal outcomes related with MSAF is crucial for improving maternal and neonatal care.

Aim: This study aims to identify the risk factors for meconium-stained liquor and evaluate the neonatal outcomes in cases with meconium-stained amniotic fluid.

Methods: This retrospective observational study at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital included 96 pregnant women with MSAF and their neonates. Data on maternal risk factors and neonatal outcomes were collected from medical records. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0 to identify significant associations, with a p-value of <0.05 considered significant. The study aimed to identify risk factors for MSAF and evaluate neonatal outcomes.

Results: The study found that advanced maternal age, nulliparity, post-term pregnancy, and pregnancy-induced hypertension were significant risk factors for MSAF. Neonates born with MSAF had lower Apgar scores at 1 minute, higher incidences of respiratory distress, and were more likely to be admitted to the NICU. There was no significant difference in birth weight between neonates with and without MSAF. These findings underline the need for close monitoring and timely intervention in high-risk pregnancies to improve neonatal outcomes.

Conclusion: Advanced maternal age, nulliparity, post-term pregnancy, and pregnancy-induced hypertension are noteworthy risk factors for MSAF. Neonates born with MSAF are at high risk for respiratory problems and NICU admission. Early identification and management of these risk factors can improve neonatal outcomes.

Recommendations: Increased monitoring and timely intervention for high-risk pregnancies can help mitigate the adverse outcomes associated with MSAF. Further research with larger sample sizes and multicenter studies is recommended to validate these findings and develop standardized management procedures.

Keywords: Meconium-Stained Amniotic Fluid, Risk Factors, Neonatal Outcomes, Respiratory Distress, Pregnancy-Induced Hypertension.

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Introduction

Meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSAF) is a significant obstetric complication, often indicating fetal distress and potential neonatal morbidity. Meconium, the infant's first stool, is typically passed after birth; however, in some cases, it is expelled into the amniotic fluid before delivery. This condition is seen in approximately 10-20% of all deliveries and is more common in post-term pregnancies. The meconium in the amniotic fluid raises concerns due to its association with adverse perinatal outcomes, including meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS), which can lead to severe respiratory complications in the newborn [1].

Understanding the risk factors for MSAF is crucial for obstetricians and pediatricians to implement timely and effective interventions. Various maternal and fetal factors have been implicated in the occurrence of MSAF, such as advanced maternal age, nulliparity, post-term pregnancy, pregnancy-induced hypertension, and intrauterine growth restriction. Identifying these risk factors can help healthcare providers anticipate and manage potential complications, thereby improving maternal and neonatal outcomes [2].

Neonates born through meconium-stained amniotic fluid are more likely to experience increased risks

of developing respiratory complications, including MAS, which can result in significant morbidity and mortality. MAS occurs when the neonate inhales MSAF fluid into the lungs, leading to airway obstruction, chemical pneumonitis, and impaired gas exchange. This condition requires prompt recognition and management to prevent long-term respiratory sequelae and other complications.

Despite the known risks associated with MSAF, there remains variability in clinical practice regarding the management of affected pregnancies and neonates. This underscores the need for further research to establish standardized protocols for the management of MSAF and to identify effective preventive measures. This study aims to contribute to the body of knowledge necessary for developing evidence-based guidelines [3].

In light of these considerations, the present study seeks to investigate the maternal risk factors associated with meconium-stained liquor and evaluate the neonatal outcomes in cases with MSAF. By analyzing data from a cohort of pregnancies complicated by MSAF, we aim to identify key predictors and outcomes that can inform clinical practice and improve both maternal and neonatal health. Our findings will provide valuable insights for healthcare providers in anticipating and managing MSAF, ultimately enhancing the quality of care for affected pregnancies.

This study aims to explore the risk factors for meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSAF) and evaluate the neonatal outcomes associated with it. By analyzing maternal characteristics and neonatal health, the study seeks to provide insights into the prevention and management of MSAF to improve maternal and neonatal care.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a reflective observational analysis aimed at identifying the risk factors associated with MSAF and evaluating the neonatal outcomes in such cases.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, a tertiary care center, over a period from July 2023 to April 2024.

Participants: The study included 96 pregnant women who delivered at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital and had documented cases of MSAF during delivery. The neonates born to these women were also included in the study for evaluation of outcomes.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Inclusion criteria encompassed all pregnant women who delivered during the study period and had MSAF document-

ed in their medical records. Exclusion criteria included women with multiple gestations, pre-existing chronic illnesses (such as diabetes or hypertension), and incomplete medical records.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize bias by ensuring the inclusion criteria were strictly adhered to and by using a standardized data collection procedure. Additionally, the analysis was conducted blind to the primary outcomes to prevent any investigator bias.

Variables: Maternal variables included age, parity, gestational age at delivery, presence of pregnancy-induced hypertension, diabetes, and delivery mode. Neonatal variables included Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes, birth weight, presence of respiratory distress, and NICU admission.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from the medical records of the participants. Information regarding maternal demographics, clinical characteristics, and neonatal outcomes were extracted and recorded using a standardized data collection form.

Procedure: Upon identification of eligible participants, their medical records were reviewed to extract relevant data. Maternal risk factors and neonatal outcomes were documented and coded for analysis. Particular attention was given to the details of the labor and delivery process, as well as immediate neonatal care and subsequent outcomes.

Statistical Analysis: The data were analyzed utilizing SPSS version 21.0. Descriptive statistics summarized the data, with continuous variables expressed as means and standard deviations, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. To compare maternal and neonatal variables between groups, inferential statistics such as chi-square tests and t-tests were employed. Statistical significance was determined with a p-value threshold of <0.05 .

Results

Maternal Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

The study included 96 pregnant women with MSAF. The mean maternal age was 29.4 ± 5.3 years. Nulliparity was observed in 38 (39.6%) of the women. The mean gestational age at delivery was 40.3 ± 1.2 weeks. Pregnancy-induced hypertension was present in 18 (18.8%) women, and gestational diabetes was observed in 12 (12.5%) women. The majority of deliveries were vaginal (64.6%), with 35.4% delivered via cesarean section.

Characteristic	Number (N=96)	Percentage (%)
Maternal Age (years, mean \pm SD)	29.4 \pm 5.3	--
Nulliparity	38	39.6
Gestational Age (weeks, mean \pm SD)	40.3 \pm 1.2	--
Pregnancy-Induced Hypertension	18	18.8
Gestational Diabetes	12	12.5
Mode of Delivery: Vaginal	62	64.6
Mode of Delivery: Cesarean	34	35.4

Neonatal Outcomes

Neonatal outcomes were assessed based on Apgar scores, birth weight, incidence of respiratory distress, and NICU admissions. The average birth weight of the neonates was 3.1 \pm 0.4 kg. The mean

Apgar scores recorded at 1 minute and 5 minutes were 6.2 \pm 1.4 and 8.3 \pm 0.8, respectively. Respiratory distress was noted in 22 (22.9%) neonates, and 28 (29.2%) required NICU admission.

Neonatal Outcome	Number (N=96)	Percentage (%)	Mean \pm SD
Birth Weight (kg, mean \pm SD)	--	--	3.1 \pm 0.4
Apgar Score at 1 Minute (mean \pm SD)	--	--	6.2 \pm 1.4
Apgar Score at 5 Minutes (mean \pm SD)	--	--	8.3 \pm 0.8
Respiratory Distress	22	22.9	--
NICU Admission	28	29.2	--

Association of Maternal Factors with MSAF

Advanced maternal age (≥ 35 years) was prominently associated with the occurrence of MSAF ($p < 0.01$). Nulliparity was also identified as a noteworthy risk factor ($p < 0.05$). Post-term pregnancy

(≥ 42 weeks) showed a strong association with MSAF ($p < 0.01$), and pregnancy-induced hypertension was significantly correlated with MSAF ($p < 0.05$). There was no significant association between gestational diabetes and MSAF ($p > 0.05$).

Risk Factor	MSAF (N=96)	p-value
Advanced Maternal Age (≥ 35 years)	24	< 0.01
Nulliparity	38	< 0.05
Post-term Pregnancy (≥ 42 weeks)	20	< 0.01
Pregnancy-Induced Hypertension	18	< 0.05
Gestational Diabetes	12	> 0.05

Neonatal Outcomes and MSAF

Neonates born with MSAF had significantly lower Apgar scores at 1 minute compared to those without MSAF ($p < 0.01$). The occurrence of respiratory distress was advanced in neonates with

MSAF ($p < 0.01$), and these neonates were more likely to be admitted to the NICU ($p < 0.01$). However, there was no noteworthy difference in birth weight between neonates with and without MSAF ($p > 0.05$).

Outcome	MSAF (N=96)	Non-MSAF (N=96)	p-value
Apgar Score at 1 Minute	6.2 \pm 1.4	7.8 \pm 1.1	< 0.01
Apgar Score at 5 Minutes	8.3 \pm 0.8	9.0 \pm 0.6	< 0.01
Respiratory Distress	22	6	< 0.01
NICU Admission	28	10	< 0.01
Birth Weight (kg, mean \pm SD)	3.1 \pm 0.4	3.2 \pm 0.3	> 0.05

The study found that advanced maternal age, nulliparity, post-term pregnancy, and pregnancy-induced hypertension were significant risk factors for MSAF. Neonates born with MSAF had lower Apgar scores at 1 minute, higher incidences of respiratory distress, and a greater likelihood of NICU admission.

These findings highlight the importance of close monitoring and timely intervention in pregnancies

at risk for MSAF. Identifying high-risk pregnancies allows healthcare providers to implement appropriate management strategies, potentially improving neonatal outcomes. The study underscores the need for further research to develop standardized protocols for the management of MSAF and to explore preventive measures.

Discussion

The results of our study align with the findings of several other investigations into the risk factors and outcomes associated with meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSAF). Similar to our study, previous research has consistently identified advanced maternal age, nulliparity, post-term pregnancy, and pregnancy-induced hypertension as significant risk factors for MSAF.

A study conducted at Felege Hiwot Comprehensive Specialized Referral Hospital in North West Ethiopia found that the prevalence of MSAF was 17.8%, with advanced maternal age and post-term pregnancies being major contributing factors. This supports our finding that advanced maternal age and post-term pregnancy significantly increase the risk of MSAF. The study also highlighted the importance of monitoring pregnancies beyond term due to the increased risk of MSAF and associated complications [4].

In terms of neonatal outcomes, our study observed that neonates born with MSAF had lower Apgar scores at 1 minute, higher incidences of respiratory distress, and increased NICU admissions. These findings are corroborated by a study published in the journal *Children*, which reported that the severity of MSAF is positively correlated with adverse neonatal outcomes such as meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS), respiratory distress, and the need for NICU admission. The study emphasized that thicker and more heavily stained meconium is associated with worse neonatal outcomes, suggesting that the degree of meconium staining should be carefully assessed during delivery to anticipate potential complications [5].

Advanced maternal age, nulliparity, post-term pregnancy, and pregnancy-induced hypertension were identified as significant risk factors for MSAF in our study. These findings align with a cross-sectional study conducted at Government Medical College, Thrissur, which also found that higher maternal age and nulliparity were significantly associated with MSAF. The study further noted that post-term pregnancies (gestational age >40 weeks) and pregnancy-induced hypertension increased the likelihood of MSAF [6].

The consistency of our findings with these previous studies underscores the importance of identifying and managing the risk factors for MSAF. Early identification of high-risk pregnancies allows for appropriate monitoring and intervention, which can significantly improve neonatal outcomes. Moreo-

ver, our study suggests that standardized protocols for the management of MSAF could further enhance the quality of care and reduce the incidence of adverse neonatal outcomes.

Conclusion

The study concluded that advanced maternal age, nulliparity, post-term pregnancy, and pregnancy-induced hypertension are significant risk factors for MSAF. Neonates born with MSAF are at an increased risk of respiratory distress and NICU admission. These findings emphasize the importance of close monitoring and timely intervention in high-risk pregnancies to improve neonatal results. Further study is recommended to develop standardized management protocols for MSAF.

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